

THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE

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Abstract:

A simple sentence consists of a single independent clause. A multiple sentence contains one or more clauses as its immediate constituents. Multiple sentences are either compound or complex. In a compound sentence the immediate constituents are two or more coordinate clause. In a complex sentence one or more of its elements, such as direct object or adverbial, are realized by a subordinate.ⁱ Simple sentence may be divided into four major syntactic classes, whose use correlates with different communicative functions;ⁱⁱ we have in Albanian and English same structure of forms e.g.

- a. The sentence that has the subject and is always present and usually precedes the verb and it is positive sentence:

The teacher will speak to the dean today.

Mësuesi do të flet me dekanin sot.

- b. The question sentence forms have three or more models of making and noun is the kernel e.g.

Will teacher speak to the dean today?

Keywords: simple, compound, complex and compound complex, sentence, Albanian, English

1. Introduction

In Albanian and English we have same structure of sentence (**simple, compound or complex sentence**). The major of elements or constituents that can be found in clauses are **subject, predicate, object, complement** etc.

ⁱ Randolph Quirk (...). (1985). **A comprehensive grammar of the English language**. London, p. 719.

ⁱⁱ Randolph Quirk. (1973). **A university grammar of English**. London, p. 191.

For Albanian and English, most linguists agree on the need to recognize at least the following word classes: **noun, verb, adjective, preposition, adverb, determinative** and **conjunction**. Each of these words classes is illustrated in the sentence below. The noun or noun phrase can be subject, object, and predicate (...) in the meaning of the structure of syntax. "The kernel sentence, then, has two main parts –a **subject** and a **predicate**. The subject consists of noun phrase, the predicate consists of the verb phrase".ⁱⁱⁱ

We may begin our inquiry into the study of syntax between Albanian and English. Both of languages have their structure which we can compare and during the study (in this chapter) we can see the different between Albanian and English (for more see from chapter 7.1.1-7.2.1). They have same **subject, predicate, object** etc. (but different structure). There are four main types of sentences: **simple, compound, complex** and **compound complex**.

By the simple sentence we can see the structure between Albanian and English, too e.g.

Maca e mbyeti miun.

S (NP) P (VP) O(NP)

The cat killed the mouse.

S (NP) P (VP) O(NP)

The noun in the simple sentence usually is the same by the structure between Albanian and English, but sometimes has some different e.g.

They are from Prishtina.

S P DO

In English language it is obligation to repeat the predicate and subject too, but in Albanian is not necessary to repeat the subject, because by the predicate we understand for what does the sentence has meaning. The sentence "**The cat killed the mouse**" we have the definite article "the" that use before the noun, and in Albanian it is contrast, it can use how suffix (Alb.) for example "**the cat -- maca**".

In both of languages we can see a lot of problems in the compound sentence, or in the complex sentence e.g.

The sentence: **The chairman^{iv} of the committee and the loquacious**

D N P D N C D Adj.

politician clashed when the meeting started.

N V C D N V

ⁱⁱⁱ Virginia Tufte. (1971). **Grammar as Style**. London, p.15.

^{iv} Shkelqim Millaku, The noun phrase, *Anglisticum*, 2013,

<http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1254>

We can see some nouns with different function in this compound sentence, it is same and in Albanian. We can consider the compound sentence has more nouns with the function **subject**, **direct** or **indirect object** etc.

In this chapter we introduce two concepts which are essential for the description, **comparative**, **contras** and **generative** of the **grammar** of noun words and noun phrase in the Albanian and English.

A complex sentence has one dependent clause (headed by a subordinating conjunction or a relative pronoun) joined to an independent clause e.g.

People who read **comics** rarely read **novels**.

Njerëzit që lexojnë **komik** rrallë lexojnë **novela**.

The man gave **me**^v a **book**.

S P IO DO

A compound-complex sentence has two independent clauses joined to one or more dependent clauses e.g.

a. Arta reads romans, **but Agroni reads novels** because books are too difficult.

Independent clause **Independent clause** dependent clause

b. Arta lexon romane **por Agroni lexon novela** sepse librat janë të vështira.

Independent clause **Independent clause** dependent clause

Grammar is traditionally subdivided into two different but inter-related areas of study – morphology and syntax. Morphology is the study of how words are formed out of smaller units (called morphemes), and so addresses question such as “what are the components morphemes of a word like *atdhedashes - patriotic...?* *Syntax is the study of the way in which phrases and sentences are structured out of words, and so addresses question like “What’s the president doing? And what is the nature of the grammatical operation by which is component words are combined together to form the overall sentence structure?”*^{vi}

According to their structure, sentences are classification into **simple**, **complex** and **compound** sentence.

Let us consider a simple sentence first. *Anna sang*.^{vii} A simple sentence has one independent clause. This is same in Albanian and English languages e.g.

Tomi lexon **librin**.^{viii}

Tome reads **the book**.

Teuta works in **the garden**.

^v Shkelqim Millaku – Xhevahire Topanica, 2016, THE INDIRECT OBJECT (IO) – ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/294/739>

^{vi} Andrew Radford. (2004). **English Syntax**. Cambridge, p. 1

^{vii} Annette Becker & Markus Bieswanger. (2006). **Introduction to English Linguistics**. Germany, p. 109.

^{viii} Shkelqim Millaku – Xhevahire Topanica, THE GENDER OF COUNTABLE AND UNCOUNTABLE NOUNS, EJELT, 2016, <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/295/742>

Teuta punon **në kopsht**.

John speaks **English** well.

Johni e flet mirë **anglishten**.

Arbeni reads a **newspaper**.

Arbeni lexon **gazeten**.

Arbeni and Teuta read **books**. (Compound^{ix} subject)

Tome and Arta read and enjoys books. (Compound verb)

Tome reads books and newspapers. (Compound direct object)

Those are the sentences that consist of only one main clause and no subclasses. The noun Anna, (Teuta, John, Arbeni) is the subject, where the sang (works, speaks, read) is the predicate. A simple sentence consists of a subject and one predicator.

Sentence level

Function

Word level

Figure 1

To indicate that both noun and the verb work are not only constituents but phrases, and we can say that the sentence **Teuta works** consists of the noun **phrase Teuta** and the verb phrase works.

The noun is the head of the simple or complex sentence. In both of languages we have spoken for the structure of morphology and syntax, but now we shall speak for clauses and clause structure whenever a statement is true in both of languages (Albanian and English) and for sentence, too e.g.

The sentence in Albanian language e.g.

Nga dera doli **një vazë** shtathedhur. (Cs)

Rr K/P K/S P

Benit iu kthye **vajza** **nga Wiена**. (Cs)

IO P K DO^{xi}

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku – Xhevahire Topanica, 2016, THE COMPOUND NOUNS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, *European Journal of Education Studies*, <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/216/513>

^x Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF NOUN PHRASES BETWEEN ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, WEI, 2016, <http://www.westeastinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Shkelqim-Millaku.pdf>

Mary is **in the flat.** (eng)

S V DO (Cs)

He gives me expensive **present.**

S V O

The daughter is sleeping. -----The daughter is asleep.

S V O (Cs)

The clause types in both of languages are productive.

The form **SVOO** clause can be transformed into **SVOA** clauses by the substitution of a **preposition phrase for the indirect object**, with the change of order and it is same in both of languages e.g.

He sent Arta's a card. ---- He sent a card to Arta.

Ai ia dërgoi Artës kartën. --- Ai e dërgoi kartën të Arta.

He left Arta's^{xii} card. ----- He left a card for Artën.

Ai ia la Artës kartën. --- Ai e dërgoi kartën për Artën.

How we see by the example the simple sentence in the both of languages have only one predicate and only one subject, object etc. The noun is the head of the simple sentence and in fact it is **subject, object, and (predicate)**.

A simple sentence consists of a single independent clause. A multiple sentence contains one or more clauses as its immediate constituents. Multiple sentences are either compound or complex. In a compound sentence the immediate constituents are two or more coordinate clause. In a complex sentence one or more of its elements, such as direct object or adverbial, are realized by a subordinate.^{xiii}

Simple sentence may be divided into four major syntactic classes, whose use correlates with different communicative functions,^{xiv} we have in Albanian and English same structure of forms e.g.

- c. The sentence that has the subject and is always present and usually precedes the verb and it is positive sentence:

The teacher will speak to the dean today.

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- d. The question sentence forms have three or more models of making and noun is the kernel e.g.

Will teacher speak to the dean today?

^{xi} Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of Direct object between Albanian and English Language, IJIR, 2016, <http://imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/view/1320>

^{xii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Genetive, Anglisticum, 2015, <http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1218>

^{xiii} Randolph Quirk (...). (1985). **A comprehensive grammar of the English language**. London, p. 719.

^{xiv} Randolph Quirk. (1973). **A university grammar of English**. London, p. 191.

Who will you speak to?

You will speak to the dean?

- e. The model of sentence which normally hasn't subject and the verb is in the imperative e.g.

Speak to the dean today.

Fol me dekanin sot.

If two or more sentences have identical or very similar structure, this parallelism connects the sentences, the connection being further reinforced by lexical equivalences and implication of semantic relationship (usually of contrast):

John put his career before his family. Bill put his family before his career.^{xv}

A sentence may be one of four kinds, depending upon the number and type(s) of clauses it contains. The noun in independent clause, dependent clause and simple sentence is the head of the meaning. It can be subject, direct object, indirect object or predicate.

In the **independent clause** contains a subject, a verb, and a complete thought e.g.
I spoke with **my teacher last week**.

A **dependent clause** sentence in Albanian and English languages has a subject and a verb, but don't have complete thought e.g.

I spoke to him **after he has past the exam**.

Unë fola më atë **pasi ai e ka kryer provimin**

In both of languages the simple sentence has one independent clause.

A **dependent clause** contains a subject and a verb, but **no complete thought**.

He studies **at University**. Ai studion në **Universitet**.

I am from **London**. Unë jam nga **Londra**.

Arta likes **play tennis**. Artës i pëlqen të **luan tenis**.

We have **two friends**. We kami dy **shokë**.

By the forms of sentence we can consider the nouns (and verbs) are the head (kernel) of sentences. Albanian and English have some kinds of simple sentences e.g.

The first model is the positive or declarative sentence e.g.

Teuta is a **student**. **Teuta** është **studente**.

He (Beni) works in the **laibrary**. **Ai (Beni)** punon në **bibliotekë**.

The second kind of sentence is called imperative because gives a command, make a request etc. e.g.

Go to your school. Shko në shkollë.

Go by bus. Shko me autobus.

Please lend me your dictionary. Ju lutem mund t'iu huazoj fjalorin tuaj.

^{xv} Ibidem, p. 308.

His father used to be rich **and** he will buy a new car.

I don't like dogs, **and** my sister doesn't like cats.

You can write on paper, **or** you can use a computer.

A tree fell onto the school roof in a storm, **but** none of the students was injured.

The noun in the simple, complex or compound sentence usually is subject, object etc. Contains two independent clauses that are joined by a coordinating conjunction. The most common coordinating conjunctions are: (Alb.) **dhe, e, edhe, as, as as...**, – (eng.) **and, or, but, so...** etc).

A. I feel to speak **Albanian**, and **my friend** feels to speak **English**.

S P DO S P DO

Beni played **football**, **so I** went **at school**.

S P DO S P DO^{xviii}

The **compound sentence** is a combination of two or more simple sentence or complex sentences. While the complex sentence has only *one* main clause, the compound has *two or more* independent clauses making statements, questions, or commands.

A compound sentence usually consists of more than one simple sentence (clause). All of the clauses in a compound sentence are independent and they are usually bound by co-coordinators, such as, and, but or and their substitutes e.g.

Everyone was in the hall and the door had been closed.^{xix}

The compound sentences in Albanian language are: (in the following all the noun we will underline)

a. **Dikush këndonte dhe të tjerët flisnin ngadalë.**

S _____ S _____ DO

b. **Shiu kishte pushuar dhe qielli ishte kthjellur.**

c. **Koha ishte me shi dhe Beni dhe unë shpejtua hapin dhe pas pak dëgjuam disa zëra duke ma thirrur, por ne nuk u ndalem, sepse nuk ia besonim se do të ndalet shiu.**

d. **Peshku në det e filterja në zjarr.**

By the Albanian sentences we can consider the noun is subject, direct and indirect object and predicate in the compound sentence. It is the same and in English language but of course with some different structure of using e.g.

A write with strong intelligence but weak invention in not likely to become a novelist. The Reverend Mr. Gaster begins Peacock's series of gourmandizing

^{xviii} Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, The direct object, Anglisticum,

<http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233/1721>

^{xix} Vesel Nuhiu. (2002). **English Syntax**. Prishtinë, p. 111.

clergymenë Panscope is his first and thinnest burlesque of Coleridge's transcendentalism.^{xx}

Arta suppose that she can use phone.

In a few minutes I'll ask him what he wants tomorrow.

Beni speaks English, but Tomi speaks Albanian.

Beni reads a book, however Arta reads a newspaper.

Toni reads newspaper, his friend reads magazine.

Arta supozon se ajo mund ta përdorë telefonin.

Për pak minuta unë do ta pyes atë çka ai dëshiron të bën nesër.

Complex sentences (fjali me nënrenditje) consist of a main clause with one or more subordinate clause. In both of languages this form of sentence is still complex by the structure. The noun is the same with function how is in the simple sentence (It can be subject, direct or indirect object, predicate etc.).

Beni reads newspaper^{xxi}, *because* the book is difficult.

Beni lexon gazetën, sepse libri është i vështirë.

This sentence is making by two sentences and the second is dependent clause. Ne do të vazhdojmë të luajmë futboll, **nëse** Agroni nuk vonohet. I met him **when** I was at the university.

In Albanian and English we have a lot of **subordinating conjunctions** and by those we can know the form of structure.

A complex sentence has an independent clause joined by one or more dependent clauses. A complex sentence always has a subordinator such as **because, since, after, although**, or when or a relative pronoun such as **that, who, which** e.g.

The students are studying **because** they have a test tomorrow.

Studentët janë duke studiuar **sepse** kanë test nesër.

Arta and Beni went to the movies **after** they finished studying.

In describing the noun phrases or *the head, around which the other constituents cluster and which dictates concord with other parts of the sentence*:

The tall **girl** standing in the corner is my **sister**.

The tall **girls** standing in the corner are my **sisters**.

[The tall **girl** standing (**which** or **who**) has a blue sweater is my **sister**.

I saw the tall **girl** in [the corner (**which** or **who**) was full of **people**.^{xxii}

^{xx} Thomas Love Peacock. (2002). **Notable British novelist**, vol. 3, New York, (USA), p. 709.

^{xxi} Shkelqim Millaku – Xhevahire Topanica, The compound nouns between English and Albanian language, EJES, <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/216>

^{xxii} Randolph Quirk & Sidney Greenbaum, (1985), **A comprehensive grammar of the English language**. New York, p.1238.

As the conclusion: In Albanian and English the complex sentence has one or more independent clause and one or more dependent clauses e.g.

Nuk ishte vështirë të parandalohet ç'qëndrim do të mbanin ata dhe ç'vendim do të merrnin.^{xxiii} This sentence has this tree of diagram:

Figure 2

This Albanian language the sentence is the complex that has one head sentence (**Nuk ishte vështirë**) and three another's sentences which are dependents how are seeing by the tree of diagram. Complex sentences use subordination to show the relative importance of ideas in a sentence.

In English language we have a lot of same sentence that the head is the noun e.g. John has worked in New York, because he liked it.

The function of noun in the simple or compound sentence can be subject, direct or indirect object, predicate nominal etc. The noun is the head in the sentence and can be complement in the simple or compound sentence.

^{xxiii} Ahmet Kelmendi, (2002). **Gramatika e gjuhës së sotme shqipe**. Prishtinë p. 112.

^{xxiv} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, Anglisticum, 2015, <http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^{xxv} Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, Anglisticum, <http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1218>

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